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Frouros: An open-source Python library for drift detection in machine learning systems

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ABSTRACT

Frouros is an open-source Python library capable of detecting drift in machine learning systems. It provides a combination of classical and more recent algorithms for drift detection, covering both concept and data drift. We have designed it to be compatible with any machine learning framework and easily adaptable to real-world use cases. The library is developed following best development and continuous integration practices to ensure ease of maintenance and extensibility.

Code metadata

Current code version	v0.8.0
Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/ElsevierSoftwareX/SOFTX-D-24-00119
Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	
Legal Code License	BSD 3-Clause License
Code versioning system used	Git
Software code languages, tools, and services used	Python
Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Python \geq 3.9 matplotlib \geq 3.8.2, <3.9 numpy \geq 1.26.3, <1.27 requests \geq 2.31.0, <2.32 scipy \geq 1.12.0, <1.14 tqdm \geq 4.66.1, <5.0
If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://frouros.readthedocs.io
Support email for questions	computing.support@ifca.unican.es

1. Motivation and significance

When deploying machine learning models in real-world applications, there is often the erroneous assumption that a given model will be used in a stationary environment, assuming that the same concepts learned during the training phase will remain valid at inference time [1], or that training samples and production-time samples will come from the same distribution [2]. However, in real-world scenarios, this is often far from always being true, and both situations may result in some type of *drift* that can end up affecting the model performance [3]. Additionally, due to the high cost of collecting and labeling samples, this performance loss can often not be confirmed in many real-world problems, and other methods that only rely on distribution changes must be used.

Traditionally, there has been little consensus on the terminology and definitions of the different types of *drift*, as stated by [4]. To adopt some clear definitions for the remainder of this paper, we apply those used

by [5] for the *concept drift* part, in combination with those used by [6] for detecting *dataset shift* using only the covariates. In order to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying drift concepts discussed in this work, we encourage readers to refer to the provided references. Therefore, we set up the following definitions assuming two different time points, t and $t + w$, where t could be any point in time, and w could be the time at which the existence of change is checked [7]. Thus, given $P(X, y) = P(y|X)P(X)$, a change in the joint distribution between two different times that can result in performance degradation can be described as $P_t(X, y) \neq P_{t+w}(X, y)$. The types of changes that can lead to degradation of the model's performance are categorized as follows:

Concept drift There is a change in the conditional probability $P(y|X)$, with or without a change in $P(X)$. Thus, it can be defined as $P_t(y|X) \neq P_{t+w}(y|X)$. Also known as *real concept drift* [5].

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Data drift There is a change in $P(X)$. Therefore, this type of drift only focuses on the distribution of the covariates, $P(X)$, so $P_t(X) \neq P_{t+w}(X)$. Also known as *covariate shift* in some contexts... Hereafter, we rename *dataset shift* [6] to *data drift*, to maintain consistency with the above definitions and with some of the related software mentioned in Section 1.1 that also refer to it as *data drift* [8,9]. A variation of *data drift* can be considered *label drift*, also known as *prior probability shift* [10], where the change occurs in the label distribution $P(Y)$ instead of the covariates $P(X)$. Thus, $P_t(Y) \neq P_{t+w}(Y)$.

In this paper, we present Frouros, an open-source Python library for drift detection in machine learning systems. The library aims to fulfill two main objectives:

1. to easily integrate into a machine learning system workflow that uses any machine learning framework, thus making it framework-agnostic; and
2. to unify in a single library the *concept drift* detection part (traditionally researched and used for streaming/evolving data streams and incremental learning as described by 11) with the research of change detection in the covariate distributions (also known as *dataset shift* or *distribution shift*, related to the field of statistical two-sample testing as introduced in 6, and methods that measure the distance between distributions as described by 12).

1.1. Related work

In terms of related software, concerning the *concept drift* detection part, MOA [13] has most of the methods that we are including, but they are implemented in Java. In Python, River [14], which is focused on online machine learning and streaming data, offers some *concept drift* detection methods, but only a subset of those presented here. Another Python library that contains this type of detector is scikit-multiflow [15], but it has not been taken into account since it was merged with the online machine learning library Crème [16], resulting in the aforementioned River library.

For the *data drift* methods, Alibi Detect [8] has several algorithms related to the field of statistical two-sample hypothesis testing, and some of them can act both online (single sample) and offline (batch sample). TorchDrift [17] also implements some statistical two-sample hypothesis testing methods, but in this case, it uses PyTorch [18] for their implementation.

To the best of our knowledge, Menelaus [9] is the only open-source library that has both *concept* and *data drift* methods, although they classify them into the following types: *change detection*, *concept drift*, and *data drift*. *Concept drift* methods are implemented in such a way that the user must necessarily be in charge of controlling each iteration of the sample without offering some helper functions or classes to interact with the detector, as Frouros does with the *callbacks* concept that is explained in Section 2.2.2.

Table 1 provides a more detailed view of the methods implemented in each of the libraries mentioned above, as well as those included in Frouros. At the time of writing this paper, Frouros is listed as the library with the highest number of available methods with 31. Moreover, several other libraries and tools have been excluded from Table 1 since they implement a more limited number of methods or are more focused on building graphical dashboards and visual representations, such as Deepchecks [19], Eurybia [20], Evidently [21], NannyML [22] or whylogs [23].

2. Software description

2.1. Software architecture

The design and implementation of the library have been carried out to make it compatible with any machine learning framework, thus making it framework-agnostic. The library, as shown in Fig. 1, is divided into the following main packages:

callbacks Frouros implements the well-known concept of *callbacks*, presented in some machine learning frameworks, such as Keras [68] and PyTorch Lightning [69], to be used by the detectors. This allows users to execute custom code at certain points. A more detailed explanation is given in Section 2.2.2.

datasets contains sample datasets that can be used for testing detectors, divided into real or synthetic, depending on whether the dataset consists of real data or if data has been artificially generated. Examples include Elec2 [70] and SEA generator [71].

detectors contains the implementation of the *concept drift* and *data drift* detection methods, according to the definitions introduced in Section 1, and how they detect it. Moreover, the package provides a shared abstract class named BaseDetector that contains the basic methods (reset) and attributes (callbacks) that detectors must implement.

metrics provides evaluation metrics such as prequential error metrics [72] to evaluate the performance of *concept drift* methods described in Section 2.2.1.

utils contains different auxiliary data structures, kernel functions, and statistical classes used in the detectors implementations.

Each of the above-mentioned packages is designed to be extensible, which eases the implementation of new detectors, callbacks, metrics, and datasets.

2.2. Software functionalities

The following section contains the description of the two packages that provide the main user-facing functionality: detectors and callbacks.

2.2.1. Detectors

Regarding the category of detector implemented, all detectors inherit from an abstract class named BaseDetector that contains the basic methods (reset) and attributes (callbacks) that each detector must implement.

Concept drift. These methods are aimed at detecting *concept drift*. To update the detector, depending on the type of algorithm, they may require either the ground-truth labels/values or the values of the variable to be tracked, which is usually a model performance metric. The detector can receive the update values on demand; therefore, it is not mandatory to feed it with all the ground-truth labels/values or model performance metric values. All implemented methods work in a streaming manner, receiving one sample at a time. In terms of implementation, each detector inherits from the BaseConceptDrift abstract class. Depending on the type of *concept drift* detector, it also inherits from its corresponding type abstract class. The update method is used to update the detector's inner state, and it checks if drift is occurring each time a new value is received. Additionally, upon instantiation, the detector can optionally receive a list of *callbacks*. It also receives a configuration class that contains specific parameters determining its behavior.

Table 1
Drift detection methods by library.

	Method	Alibi-detect	Menelaus	MOA	River	TorchDrift	Frouros	Reference	
Concept drift	ADWIN		✓	✓	✓		✓	[24]	
	BOCD						✓	[25]	
	CUSUM		✓	✓			✓	[26]	
	DDM		✓	✓	✓		✓	[1]	
	ECDD-WT			✓			✓	[27]	
	EDDM		✓	✓	✓		✓	[28]	
	GMA			✓			✓	[29]	
	HDDM-A			✓	✓		✓	[30]	
	HDDM-W			✓	✓		✓	[30]	
	KSWIN				✓		✓	[31]	
	LFR		✓					✓	[32]
	Page Hinkley		✓	✓	✓		✓	[26]	
	RDDM			✓			✓	[33]	
	SEED			✓				✓	[34]
	SeqDrift1			✓				✓	[35]
	SeqDrift2			✓				✓	[36]
	STEPD		✓	✓			✓	✓	[37]
	MD3		✓					✓	[38]
Data drift	Anderson–Darling test						✓	[39]	
	Bhattacharyya Distance						✓	[40]	
	BWS test						✓	[41]	
	C2ST	✓						[42]	
	CDBD		✓					[43]	
	Context-aware MMD	✓						[44]	
	Cramér-von Mises test	✓					✓	[45]	
	Earth Mover’s Distance					✓	✓	[46]	
	Energy Distance						✓	[47]	
	Fisher’s Exact test	✓						✓	[48]
	Hellinger Distance						✓	[49]	
	HDDDM		✓					✓	[50]
	Histogram Intersection						✓	✓	[51]
	Incremental KS test						✓	✓	[52]
	JS Divergence						✓	✓	[53]
	kdq-Tree		✓					✓	[54]
	KL Divergence						✓	✓	[55]
	Kolmogorov–Smirnov test	✓				✓	✓	✓	[56]
	Kuiper’s test						✓	✓	[57]
	Learned Kernel MMD	✓						✓	[58]
	LSDD	✓						✓	[59]
	Mann–Whitney U test						✓	✓	[60]
	MMD	✓					✓	✓	[61]
NN-DVI		✓					✓	[62]	
Partial MMD						✓	✓	[63]	
PCA-CD		✓					✓	[64]	
PSI							✓	[65]	
Welch’s t-test							✓	[66]	
χ^2 test	✓						✓	[67]	
# Methods		9	13	14	7	4	31		

Fig. 1. Frouros high-level overview of the main packages.

Data drift. These methods focus on detecting changes by considering only the covariates. Therefore, these algorithms try to detect changes at a feature level by comparing new data distributions against reference data distributions. Depending on the number of samples given to the detector to compare with the reference distribution, these methods can be classified as *batch* or *streaming*. The former uses a batch of samples to test against the reference distribution, and the latter can receive one

sample at a time to update the inner state of the detector; therefore, the samples must follow a sequential order. Unlike *concept drift* detectors, there is a `fit` method that stores the samples from the reference distribution used for comparison at inference time.

In some cases, certain calculations are pre-computed to subsequently reduce execution time when comparing new data with the reference distribution. In the case of batch algorithms, the compare

method is used to carry out the comparison and obtain a statistic or distance value depending on the type of detector. Whereas for the streaming detectors, an `update` method is used each time a new sample is added to the detector. Based on the type of *data drift* detector (statistical test or distance-based), checking if drift is taking place is done in different ways. After calling the `compare` or `update` methods, statistical tests provide the corresponding p -value that determines if drift exists. For distance-based detectors, the output is only the distance between the provided data and the data from the reference distribution. Therefore, through the use of *callbacks*, explained in Section 2.2.2, p -values can be obtained for these types of detectors. Moreover, *data drift* detectors are implemented considering the type of data that they are expected to work with (categorical or numerical) and the number of features that can be considered (univariate or multivariate).

As mentioned in Section 1, *data drift* methods can also be used for detecting *label drift* by considering the label distribution. Consequently, the described way of using the detectors for *data drift* applies to *label drift*.

2.2.2. Callbacks

Execution of custom code at certain points is possible through the use of *callbacks*. This adds enough flexibility to `Frouros` to be adapted to real-world use cases required by users. *Callbacks* are divided according to whether the detector belongs to the batch or streaming category.

For batch detectors, *callbacks* inherit from the `BaseCallbackBatch` class, which provides methods such as `on_compare_start` and `on_compare_end`. These methods can be implemented to execute custom code before and after the comparison against the reference distribution is made.

In the case of streaming detectors, similar methods are provided for the `update` method. All *callback* detectors share `on_fit_start` and `on_fit_end` provided by `BaseCallback`, since *data drift* detectors can be categorized as batch or streaming.

Some examples of *callbacks* already implemented and ready to use in the library include tracking the history of a *concept drift* detector, computing p -values through the use of permutation tests [73] (including exact p -values [74]) in distance-based *data drift* detectors, among others.

2.3. Development

Intending to follow a set of open-source software development standards that allow the maintainability and extensibility of the library over time, we emphasize the following aspects:

Continuous integration: A continuous integration workflow based on GitHub Actions ensures that new modifications easily integrate with the existing code base and are compatible with multiple Python versions.

Documentation: An API documentation is provided using Sphinx and hosted on the Read the Docs¹ website. The documentation includes both basic and advanced examples of the use of these detection methods.

Quality code: To ensure minimum standards in terms of code quality, code coverage is set to be greater than 90%, and some Python quality and style tools that comply with PEP8 standards [75] are used, such as `ruff` and `mypy`. Optionally, developers can also make use of `pre-commit` hooks.

Open-source: In addition to the source code being available on GitHub,² `Frouros` package can be installed through the Python Package Index (PyPI).³ In terms of licensing, it is distributed under the BSD-3-Clause license.

3. Illustrative examples

We provide the following examples to demonstrate how `Frouros` can be used with some of the implemented methods to detect drift.

3.1. Example 1: Concept drift

We demonstrate the detection of *concept drift* using the Drift Detection Method (DDM) [1] with different artificial concepts generated in SEA [71], where a concept or block is defined by the following rule:

$$\text{class}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_1 + x_2 \leq \theta \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Here, x_1 and x_2 are two features (there is a third feature x_3 , which is irrelevant to the decision boundary), and θ is a threshold that differentiates the two classes. Four different concepts/blocks are defined based on the value of θ : Concept 1 ($\theta = 8$), Concept 2 ($\theta = 9$), Concept 3 ($\theta = 7$), and Concept 4 ($\theta = 9.5$).

In this case, Concepts 1 and 3 are used without any added noise. Concept 1 is employed for training a model, warming up the detector, and also during the testing phase. On the other hand, Concept 3 is only used to induce *concept drift* during the testing phase.

The two different concepts are represented in two distinct phases: the warm-up phase, where $\theta_{\text{warm-up}}(t) = 8$ (Concept 1), and the testing phase, where Concept 1 is initially used to demonstrate that the same concept does not trigger the detector. Later, Concept 3 is introduced to trigger a drift signal:

$$\theta_{\text{test}}(t) = \begin{cases} 8 & \text{if } 0 \leq t < 10000 \\ 7 & \text{if } 10000 \leq t < 20000 \end{cases}$$

We use a straightforward approach by fitting a decision tree classifier to the training dataset. For the first 10,000 samples, we warm up the detector with samples from Concept 1, and then the detector is ready to start checking for drift. Subsequently, we feed both the model and the detector with 10,000 samples coming from Concept 1 to check that the detector does not produce a false positive in terms of detecting *drift*. Finally, 10,000 samples from Concept 3 are provided, and *concept drift* is detected by the detector a few samples after starting to receive this kind of samples. Fig. 2 depicts the previous simulation process.

Various metrics are employed and monitored; in this scenario, we focus on the prequential error [72], using different fading factors: $\alpha = 1.0$, $\alpha = 0.9999$, and $\alpha = 0.999$.

3.2. Example 2: Data drift

Here, we demonstrate the use of Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) [61], which is a popular technique for multivariate two-sample testing [6], along with a permutation test callback as a *data drift* detector over the MNIST [76] image dataset to simulate a *drift* process at the feature level that would likely affect the performance of the machine learning model in charge of classifying the digits. We fit the detector with a reference sample of 1000 original MNIST images and set aside another 10,000 sample images to test for the presence of *data drift*.

For the test sample, we perform three independent checks for *data drift*: one in which the test sample remains unmodified (original), another applying GaussianBlur, and the last one applying ElasticTransform, resulting in images like the ones depicted in Fig. 3. Regarding the

¹ <https://frouros.readthedocs.io>

² <https://github.com/IFCA/frouros>

³ <https://pypi.org/project/frouros>

Fig. 2. Stream simulation with Concepts 1 and 3 from SEA [71], using Drift Detection Method (DDM) as the *drift* detector and a decision tree as the ML model.

Fig. 3. Sample images for each MNIST class. Fig. 3(a) shows a sample without applying any transformation. Figs. 3(b) and 3(c) apply GaussianBlur and ElasticTransform respectively to induce data drift.

Table 2

Results of detecting *data drift* after applying GaussianBlur and ElasticTransform transformations on all MNIST test set images.

Method	Distance ($\times 10^{-4}$)	p-value	Data drift (exist./detect.)	Accuracy
Reference	-2.62	0.7219	False/False	0.9898
GaussianBlur	82.76	≤ 0.01	True/True	0.9671
ElasticTransform	75.05	≤ 0.01	True/True	0.8261

transformations, both GaussianBlur and ElasticTransform are present in torchvision [77].

We set the significance level $\alpha = 0.01$ to perform the hypothesis test and estimate each p -value using 5×10^3 permutations. The results for the permutation tests are shown in Fig. 4, where, as expected, both applied transformations are detected as drift ($p \leq 0.01$), and the unmodified images (original) do not suffer from drift ($p > 0.01$). In addition, Table 2, provides a more detailed view, where accuracy drops from 0.9898 to 0.9671 for GaussianBlur and to 0.8261 in the case of ElasticTransform.

For brevity, the details and source code of *Example 1: Concept drift*⁴ and *Example 2: Data drift*⁵ are omitted. However, both the details and source code are available in the GitHub repository and the documentation, along with more practical examples.

4. Impact

Monitoring models' behavior and performance is key for quality, reliable and trustworthy machine learning systems. Although a vast number of drift detection methods exist in the literature (c.f. Section 1.1), drift detection and monitoring is still not widespread. In this context, Frouros is one of the first software libraries implementing algorithms for both *concept* and *data drift* detection, facilitating

⁴ https://frouros.readthedocs.io/en/v0.7.1/examples/concept_drift/DDM_advance.html

⁵ https://frouros.readthedocs.io/en/v0.7.1/examples/data_drift/MMD_advance.html

Fig. 4. Permutation test for each MNIST test dataset. Fig. 4(a) shows the permutation test for the reference samples, where not *data drift* is detected. Figs. 4(b) and 4(c) depict GaussianBlur and ElasticTransform permutation tests respectively, in which *data drift* is correctly detected.

research in the domain of machine learning system robustness through a unified programming interface. Leveraging Frouros, researchers and machine learning developers can explore and apply *drift* detectors in real-world situations, including those detection algorithms easily in their development and deployment pipelines. By doing so, it will be possible to detect unexpected situations in a machine learning application with a robust detection system, and not by simply relying on monitoring dashboards.

Since Frouros groups well-known *concept* and *data drift* detection methods in a single library, it can be used in two ways:

1. Directly integrating one or multiple detectors into a machine learning pipeline, making Frouros ready for use in a production environment, providing users of the pipeline with robust drift detection methods (that can trigger an alert, stop the pipeline, or perform any other relevant action in case of *drift*).
2. Allowing researchers and developers to implement their detectors by extending existing abstract classes or including new datasets. This facilitates performance comparison between different *drift* detection methods and datasets.

Frouros is being actively used as the reference tool for drift detection in two European research projects: “Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud (AI4EOSC)”⁶ and “Imaging data and services for aquatic science (iMagine)”⁷ where it is being used as part of the deployment and operations of machine learning systems. Besides Frouros has already surpassed a hundred stars on its GitHub repository, which is a sign of the good reception by the user community. Additionally, we have designed it following a set of best practices for ease of maintenance and extensibility, as described in Section 2.3. This allows new users to easily contribute to the codebase, aiming to gather a larger user and developer active community.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents Frouros, an open-source Python library for drift detection in machine learning systems that can be used with any machine learning framework, both for methods that aim to detect

⁶ <https://ai4eosc.eu>

⁷ <https://imagine-ai.eu>

concept drift and those that try to detect *data drift*. Moreover, this library provides enough flexibility to adapt to the user's workflow through the so-called *callbacks* concept, which is also used in other well-known machine learning libraries. Additionally, Frouros aims to meet open-source software development standards that allow for easy extension, both in terms of adding new methods or *callbacks*.

For future work, in addition to regularly adding new detection methods, we plan to improve the performance of *concept drift* methods using Python code optimizers like Cython [78] and adapt *data drift* methods to be used on GPUs. Furthermore, adding new *callbacks*, as described in Section 2.2.2, would enable the library to handle even more real-world use cases.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jaime Céspedes Sisniega: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Álvaro López García:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data used for example generation is included in the source code.

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